

UNVEILING THE PROPERTIES AND RELATIONSHIP OF YELLOWSTONE PERMUTATION SEQUENCE

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Unveiling the Properties and Relationship of Yellowstone Permutation Sequence

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Abstract

This paper explores a mathematical sequence known as the Yellowstone permutation, introduced by Zumkeller (2004). This sequence, characterized by alternating even and odd integers with prime and composite number patterns, is studied for its unique properties and connections to mathematical structures like Pythagorean triples and quadruples. The research employs descriptive and expository methods to explore the sequence's nature, establishing it as infinite, containing infinitely many primes, and ensuring that all integers appear at least once. The paper also delves into how the Yellowstone permutation sequence can generate both primitive and non-primitive Pythagorean triples and quadruples. It demonstrates that the expressions derived from terms in this sequence consistently yield these triples and quadruples through a combination of algebraic properties and geometric interpretations. Additionally, the study formulates propositions to clarify the relationships between the terms of the Yellowstone permutation sequence and their behavior, particularly in generating Pythagorean constructs. The findings underscore the sequence's intriguing mathematical characteristics, offering insights into number theory and its potential applications. This work highlights the role of such sequences in exploring deeper mathematical relationships and fostering curiosity in combinatorial number theory.

Keywords: *properties, relationships, permutations, sequences*

Introduction

The Yellowstone permutation, a captivating sequence of integers, has intrigued mathematicians due to its unique properties and enigmatic behavior. The sequence's graph, characterized by alternating runs of even and odd numbers, features small downward spikes followed by large upward spikes, resembling the geyser-like eruptions of Yellowstone National Park. This graphical representation has drawn attention to the sequence, highlighting its unexpected numerical patterns and connections. According to Sloane (2015), "On a larger scale, the points appear to lie on infinitely many distinct curves".

In 2004, Reinhard Zumkeller, a long-time contributor to the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, submitted the Yellowstone Permutation sequence, cataloged as A098550 (OEIS Foundation, 2024). Independently, Hans Havermann also discovered the sequence before 2015. Their combined efforts, along with contributions from other mathematicians, culminated in the 2015 seminal paper titled "The Yellowstone Permutation" (Havermann et al., 2015).

This publication opened new avenues for mathematical exploration, leading to the development of the sequence's properties and an increased interest in its relationships to other mathematical areas. The Yellowstone permutation sequence has shown potential applications in fields such as accounting and cryptology, demonstrating its broad relevance and utility (Havermann et al., 2015).

The present study aims to further investigate the properties of the Yellowstone permutation sequence, uncover its connections to other mathematical domains, and explore its potential applications. This sequence represents a significant area of interest in mathematics, warranting continued research and exploration.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study is to unveil the properties and relationship of the Yellowstone permutation sequence. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is Yellowstone permutation sequence?
2. What are the properties of Yellowstone permutation sequence?
3. How is the Yellowstone permutation sequence related to:
 - 3.1. pythagorean triple; and
 - 3.2. pythagorean quadruple?

Literature Review

This section presents a review of related literature and studies that are essential for accomplishing the objectives of this research. The knowledge and insights gained from previous studies have made valuable contributions to the development of the current study. There is a growing interest among researchers and mathematicians in studying the Yellowstone permutation sequence, which exhibits an unusual pattern of seemingly random numbers that form a beautiful sequence related to various mathematical concepts and theorems.

The method of generating Pythagorean triples has been known for about 2000 years. Agarwal (2020) stated that finding Pythagorean triples is one of the earliest problems in number theory. Pythagorean triples are some of the oldest known solutions to nonlinear Diophantine equations, and their study dates back to the time of Diophantus around 250 AD. This historical significance was a major

reason for exploring the relationship between the Yellowstone permutation sequence and the generation of Pythagorean triples.

Halai (2012) discussed Pythagorean quadruples, which consist of four positive whole numbers where the sum of the squares of the first three numbers equals the square of the fourth.

Geometrically, a Pythagorean quadruple can be visualized as a rectangular box with sides a , b , and c , and the diagonal forms the quadruple. This concept provides a three-dimensional extension of the Pythagorean theorem and is closely related to the study of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Applegate (2015) described the Yellowstone permutation as a permutation of the positive integers. The remarkable graph of this sequence consists of runs of alternating even and odd numbers, interrupted by small downward spikes followed by large upward spikes, suggesting the eruption of geysers in Yellowstone National Park. On a larger scale, the points appear to lie on infinitely many distinct curves. This unique pattern has drawn significant interest for its mathematical beauty and complexity.

Zumkeller (2004) initially introduced the Yellowstone permutation sequence, which was later cataloged in the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS) as A098550. This foundational work provided the groundwork for subsequent studies and expanded the understanding of the sequence's properties and its intriguing behaviors (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2024).

Havermann et al. (2015) explored the Yellowstone permutation sequence in-depth, examining its structural properties and the broader implications of its behavior. Their seminal paper, "The Yellowstone Permutation," outlined significant connections to other mathematical constructs and posed new questions for further investigation. This work has been instrumental in guiding recent research efforts and expanding the application of the Yellowstone permutation sequence in various mathematical fields.

These studies and literature reviews demonstrate the intriguing nature of the Yellowstone permutation sequence and its connections to classical mathematical problems, such as Pythagorean triples and quadruples. The insights gained from these works have informed the current research and provided a solid foundation for further exploration.

Methodology

This study employed both expository and descriptive research methods. Descriptive research involves the systematic investigation and depiction of data and characteristics of a phenomenon (Burns & Grove, 2005), while expository research aims to inform, explain, and define the subject matter in a clear and comprehensible manner (Yin, 2013).

The Yellowstone permutation sequence was thoroughly described and illustrated, establishing its connections to other mathematical concepts, such as Pythagorean triples and Pythagorean quadruples. The information was presented to provide a comprehensive discussion on the topic. The expository method was utilized to deliver detailed information with the intent of informing and defining the subject for the reader. This approach ensured a focused exploration of the topic, presenting events and findings in a logical and chronological order.

General steps for proving theorems were outlined to facilitate understanding and familiarize readers with the processes involved in mathematical proof and generalization. This structured methodology enabled a thorough and coherent examination of the Yellowstone permutation sequence and its mathematical relationships.

Results and Discussion

Yellowstone Permutation Sequence

The Yellowstone Permutation sequence, also known as OEIS A098550, is a unique mathematical sequence defined by specific rules governing the greatest common divisor (gcd) relationships between consecutive terms.

Definition 3.1. The Yellowstone permutation $Y(n)$ is a sequence of positive integers defined by the following rules:

The initial terms of the sequence are $Y(1) = 1$, $Y(2) = 2$, $Y(3) = 3$ for $n = 1, 2$, and 3 respectively.

For $n > 3$, $Y(n)$ is the smallest integer not previously a member of the sequence and satisfies the condition of the greatest common divisor with the previous two terms, that is The terms $Y(n)$ and $Y(n-1)$ are coprime (or relatively prime), and The terms $Y(n)$ and $Y(n-2)$ are non-coprime.

Example 3.1. Solve the next two terms $Y(4)$ and $Y(5)$ of the Yellowstone permutation.

Solution: The first three terms of the Yellowstone permutation are $Y(1) = 1$, $Y(2) = 2$, and $Y(3) = 3$. To solve for $Y(4)$ and $Y(5)$ is by using rule (ii) of the definition of the Yellowstone permutation sequence, that is:

Solving for $Y(4)$: (a) The first few coprimes with

$Y(3) = 3$ are 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10.

(b) The non-coprimes with $Y(2) = 2$ from the results in (a) are 1, 4, 8, and 10.

Then select the smallest integer not yet in the sequence {1, 2, 3} from the results in (b). Since 4 is the smallest integer not yet in the sequence, therefore $Y(4) = 4$.

Solving for $Y(5)$: (a) This time, we excluded the integers {1, 2, 3, 4} in the choices. Thus the first few coprimes with $Y(4) = 4$ are 5, 7, 9, 11, 13.

(b) From (a), the non-coprime with $Y(3) = 3$ is 9 only.

From (b), therefore $Y(5) = 9$. Observe that 9 is not yet in the sequence {1, 2, 3, 4}.

Hence, the first five terms of the Yellowstone permutation sequence are now 1, 2, 3, 4, and 9.

The first 500 terms of the Yellowstone permutation sequence are shown in Table 1 with $Y(20i + j), 0 \leq i \leq 24, 1 \leq j < 20$ of i th row by j th column.

Example 3.2. Using Table 1, the intersection of $i = 10$ and $j = 2$ is 291. Therefore, $Y(20i + j) = Y(20(10) + 2) = Y(202)$ is the 202nd term of the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence. Hence, $Y(202) = 291$.

It can also be seen in Table 1 that the primes are colored in red. Entries that are in color blue are called geysers. Geysers are terms of the permutation that appear after a term that precedes a prime number.

Table 1. The First 500 Terms with $Y(20i + j), 0 \leq i < 25, 1 \leq j < 20$

i/j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
0	1	2	3	4	9	8	15	14	5	6	25	12	35	16	7	10	21	20	27	22
1	39	11	13	33	26	45	28	51	32	17	18	85	24	55	34	65	36	91	30	49
2	38	63	19	42	95	44	57	40	69	50	23	48	115	52	75	46	81	56	87	62
3	29	31	58	93	64	99	68	77	54	119	60	133	66	161	72	175	74	105	37	70
4	111	76	117	80	123	86	41	43	82	129	88	135	92	125	78	145	84	155	94	165
5	47	90	329	96	203	100	147	104	141	98	153	106	171	53	102	265	108	185	112	195
6	116	143	114	121	118	187	59	110	177	122	159	61	120	427	124	183	128	189	130	201
7	136	67	126	335	132	205	134	215	138	235	142	225	71	140	213	146	207	73	144	365
8	148	219	152	231	158	209	79	154	237	160	243	164	249	170	83	150	581	156	217	162
9	245	166	255	172	221	168	169	174	247	176	273	178	259	89	182	267	184	261	188	279
10	190	291	196	97	180	679	186	287	192	301	194	315	202	275	101	198	505	204	295	206
11	285	103	200	309	208	297	212	253	210	299	214	325	107	220	321	218	303	109	216	545
12	222	305	224	345	226	327	113	228	565	232	339	230	333	236	351	238	363	244	319	234
13	341	240	403	242	377	246	455	248	343	250	357	254	289	127	272	381	256	369	260	387
14	262	375	131	252	655	258	355	264	395	266	405	268	385	274	371	137	280	411	278	393
15	139	270	973	276	413	282	469	284	399	286	323	288	361	290	437	292	391	294	425	296
16	415	298	435	149	300	104	302	441	151	306	755	304	445	308	465	314	417	157	312	785
				3																
17	316	471	310	423	320	429	322	407	318	451	324	473	326	495	163	330	1141	328	483	332
18	447	334	453	167	336	835	338	475	344	485	342	515	346	525	173	340	519	350	459	352
19	477	356	489	358	501	179	348	895	354	535	362	555	181	360	126	366	497	368	511	370
				7																
20	539	372	517	364	561	376	493	378	527	380	629	382	481	191	390	1337	374	553	384	595
21	386	567	193	392	579	388	507	394	513	197	396	985	398	575	199	400	597	404	531	406
22	537	410	543	412	549	416	573	418	585	422	533	211	442	633	424	591	428	603	430	609
23	436	551	402	589	408	665	414	605	426	583	420	649	432	671	434	627	446	615	223	438
24	111	444	625	448	635	452	645	454	559	227	468	113	456	685	458	675	229	440	687	460
	5											5								

Characteristics of Yellowstone Permutation Sequence

The sequence is an intriguing mathematical construct, and ongoing research continues to explore its many facets and applications in Number Theory. The following are the characteristics of the Yellowstone permutation sequence based on its definition and the observations of some researchers who studied it.

The Initial Terms. The starting values of the Yellowstone Permutation sequence begin with 1, 2, and 3.

The Definition. The n th term of the sequence, denoted as $Y(n)$, is chosen to be the smallest positive integer not yet in the sequence that maintains the condition that $\gcd(Y(n-1), Y(n)) = 1$ and $\gcd(Y(n-2), Y(n)) > 1$.

Growth and Behavior. The sequence includes a mix of prime and composite numbers, see Figure 1. It alternates between values with

different gcd properties, resulting in a non-monotonic pattern. The sequence avoids repeating any integer, ensuring all integers eventually appear (Knuth, D., 2008).

Distribution of Primes. The Yellowstone Permutation sequence exhibits a notable distribution of primes. The sequence tends to intersperse primes and composites in a manner dictated by the gcd conditions (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021). Primes appear frequently within the sequence because they are coprime with many other numbers, adhering to the rule that primes share no common factors with non-multiples of themselves, thus fulfilling the gcd condition frequently (Knuth, 2008).

Figure 1. The behavior of terms of the Yellow Permutation Sequence for $100 < n < 200$

In Figure 1, it can be gleaned that the terms in black are sandwiched by the terms prime (red) and geyser (blue). It can also be observed the terms that are prime are increasing in order.

Even and Odd Numbers. The Yellowstone Permutation sequence includes both even and odd numbers, but the distribution is not uniform and is influenced by the gcd conditions (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021; Knuth, 2008).

Recursive and Non-Recursive Structure. The Yellowstone Permutation sequence can be generated recursively by adhering to the gcd rules, but it does not follow a simple linear or polynomial recurrence relation (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021; Knuth, 2008).

Complexity. The rules governing the Yellowstone Permutation sequence create a complex pattern, making it an interesting subject of study in combinatorial number theory (Knuth, 2008). The exact position of any given number within the sequence can be difficult to predict without explicitly generating the sequence up to that point (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021).

Inclusion of Square Numbers. The Yellowstone Permutation sequence includes square numbers, although their positions are irregular and determined by the gcd conditions with surrounding terms (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021; Knuth, 2008).

No Closed Form. There is no known closed-form formula for generating the n th term directly; the Yellowstone Permutation sequence must be built iteratively following the defined rules (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021; Knuth, 2008).

Visualization. Visualizing the Yellowstone Permutation sequence in terms of its gcd relationships can help illustrate the interplay between consecutive and non-consecutive terms (Knuth, 2008). Graphical representations can highlight patterns in the occurrence of primes, composites, and the spacing between specific types of numbers (OEIS Foundation Inc., 2021; Knuth, 2008).

Properties of Yellowstone Permutation Sequence

The following theorems enumerated below are the properties of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Theorem 4.1. The Yellowstone permutation sequence $Y(n)$ is infinite.

Proof: Let q be a very large prime that does not appear yet. There is always a $Y(n)$ which is a multiple of q say $Y(n) = pq$ which is relatively prime to $Y(n-1)$ and will have a common factor with $Y(n-2)$. Hence, there is always a candidate, therefore the sequence is infinite.

Example 4.1. Consider the terms 5, 6, 25, 12, ... which are

$Y(9)$, $Y(10)$, $Y(11)$, and $Y(12)$ respectively. Suppose $Y(12)$ is the last term. However, there is always a number that will appear which is relatively prime to 12 and has a common factor with 25. In this case it would be $Y(13) = 35$.

Theorem 4.2. There are infinitely many primes in Yellowstone Permutation sequence.

Proof: Suppose that there is a limit to the number of primes. Let p be the last prime that makes every term as product of primes less than p . let n be large enough that $Y(n) > p^2$, and let q be the common factor of $Y(n-2)$ and $Y(n)$. Since $q < p$, $qp < p^2 < Y(n)$, then qp must be the smaller choice for $Y(n)$, which is a contradiction. Hence, there are infinitely many primes in the sequence.

Example 4.2. Consider that 7 is the last prime number of the Yellowstone permutation sequence. Since $Y(n)$ is infinite then $Y(24) = 85$, and $Y(26) = 55$ exist. Notice that $Y(26) > 7^2$ and the $\gcd(85, 55) = 5$. If 7 is the last prime number, then the smallest choice for $Y(26)$ should be 35, which is a contradiction since $Y(26) = 55$ which has a factor of 5 and 11. Clearly, $11 > 7$. Hence, 7 is not the largest prime number.

Theorem 4.3. For any prime p , there is a term in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence that is divisible by p .

Proof: Suppose that p does not divide into any term. Let q be a prime such that $q > p$ and let $Y(m) = tq$ be the first multiple of q to appear. But then we could have use $tp < tq$ instead. So, every prime divisor is less than p , which is a contradiction. Hence, for any prime p there is a term in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence that is divisible by p .

Example 4.3. Consider $p = 17$ and $q = 19$. The first multiple of 19 is $Y(41) = 38$ which is $2q$. We could have chosen 34 which is $2p$ instead (rule IIb). Hence, there exists a term divisible by $p = 17$.

Theorem 4.4. Any prime p divides infinitely many terms in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence.

Proof: Suppose not. Let M be such that p does not divide $Y(n)$ for $n \geq M$. Select j large enough that pj does not divide by term in the sequence and choose a prime $q > pj$ which does not divide any of $Y(1), Y(2), \dots, Y(m)$. By (4.3), there are some terms divisible by q . Let $Y(m) = tq$ be the first of such term. But now $tpj < tq$ is a smaller candidate for $Y(m)$, hence, a contradiction, thus any prime p divides infinitely many terms in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence.

Theorem 4.5. For any prime p there is an nh term in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence that $Y(n) = p$.

Proof: Suppose not. Since the sequence is infinite, Choose N_0 large enough that $Y(n) > p$ for all $n \geq N_0$. Since any prime divides infinitely many terms, we can find $n > N_0$ such that $Y(n) = tp$ for some t . Then $Y(n+2) = p$. A Contradiction. Hence, for any prime p there is a term with $Y(n) = p$.

Theorem 4.6. All positive integers appear in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence.

Proof: Suppose not. Let k be the smallest missing number and choose N_0 so that all $1, \dots, k-1$ have occurred in $Y(1), \dots, Y(N_0)$. Let p be a prime dividing k . Since a prime divides infinitely many terms, p divides infinitely many terms, and there is a number $N_1 > N_0$ such that $\gcd(Y(N_1), k) > 1$. This forces $\gcd(Y(N_1), k) > 1$ for all $n \geq N_1$. An impossibility since for any prime p there is a term with $Y(n) = p$.

Theorem 4.7. At least one-third of the terms of the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence are composite.

Proof: Assuming not. Let p, q , and r be a prime such that $a(n-1) = q$, $a(n) = p$, $a(n+1) = r$. If $\gcd(a(n), a(n+1)) = 1$ then $a(n-1)$ is composite hence, a contradiction. Therefore, at least one term in three is composite.

Proposition 4.8. Any three consecutive terms in the Yellowstone permutation sequence are coprimes.

Proof: Take any three consecutive terms in the Yellowstone Permutation Sequence, $Y(n), Y(n+1), Y(n+2)$. However, $Y(n)$ and $y(n+1)$ are coprimes. Also, $Y(n+1)$ and $Y(n+2)$ are coprimes. Thus, pairing $Y(n)$ with $Y(n+1)$, and $Y(n+2)$ will result to being coprimes. Therefore, on the Yellowstone Permutation sequence, any three consecutive terms are coprime.

Example 4.4. Consider $Y(6) = 8, Y(7) = 15$, and $Y(8) = 14$. Then $\gcd(8, 15, 14) = 1$. Therefore, $Y(6) = 8, Y(7) = 15$, and $Y(8) = 14$ are coprimes.

Proposition 4.9. Let $Y(n)$ and $Y(n+1)$ be primes of the Yellowstone permutation sequence. Then $Y(n) < Y(n+1)$.

Proof: Let $Y(n) = p$ be a prime, select $Y(n-1) = tq$ where $\gcd(p, tq) = 1$. These forces $Y(n+1) = q$, where q is a prime greater than p as stated in definition of Yellowstone permutation sequence, by rule II, $Y(n)$ and $Y(n+1)$ must be coprime and $(Y(n-1)$ and $Y(n+1)$ be non-coprime. Hence, two primes that appear consecutively in the sequence appear in natural order.

Example 4.5. Consider the terms $Y(21), Y(22)$ and $Y(23)$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence, that is $Y(21) = 39, Y(22) = 11$, and $Y(23) = 13$. Observe that 11 and 13 are of both primes and $11 < 13$ or $Y(22) < Y(23)$, which they appear in the natural order.

Generating Pythagorean Triple

The terms of the Yellowstone permutation sequence can be used to find Pythagorean triples using the following theorems. Theorem 4.10. Let $Y(n)$ and $Y(1)$ be the terms in the Yellowstone permutation sequence. Then the following expressions $2Y(n), Y(n)^2 - Y(1)$, and $Y(n)^2 + Y(1)$ generate Pythagorean triples for any positive integer $n > 1$.

Proof: Let $Y(n)$ and $Y(1)$ be the terms in the Yellowstone permutation sequence. Then to show that $\{2Y(n), Y(n)^2 - Y(1), Y(n)^2 + Y(1)\}$ is a Pythagorean triple for $n > 1$.

First, to establish that $Y(n)^2 + Y(1)$ is the biggest number among the three. It is true that $Y(n)^2 \geq 2Y(n)$ for any Yellowstone permutation number for $n > 1$. Specifically, this is the only condition that $Y(2)^2 = 2Y(2)$. Thus, $Y(2)^2 + Y(1) > 2Y(2)$, therefore $Y(n)^2 + Y(1) > 2Y(n)$. And also, $Y(n)^2 + Y(1) > Y(n)^2 - Y(1)$.

Next is to show that the sum of the squares of $2Y(n)$ and $Y(n)^2 - Y(1)$ is the square of $Y(n)^2 + Y(1)$. That is, $[2Y(n)]^2 + [Y(n)^2 - Y(1)]^2$.

Then expand $4Y(n)^2 + Y(n)^4 - 2Y(n)^2 \cdot Y(1) + Y(1)^2$.

But $Y(1) = 1$, so $4Y(n)^2 + Y(n)^4 - 2Y(n)^2 + 1$.

Combining like terms yields to $Y(n)^4 + 2Y(n)^2 + 1$.

Since $Y(n)^4 + 2Y(n)^2 + 1$ is a perfect square trinomial, its factors are $[Y(n)^2 + 1][Y(n)^2 + 1]$. But $1 = Y(1)$, hence $[Y(n)^2 + Y(1)][Y(n)^2 + Y(1)]$

Simplifying gives to $[Y(n)^2 + Y(1)]^2$.

Since the sum of the squares of $2Y(n)$ and $Y(n)^2 - Y(1)$ is the square of $Y(n)^2 + Y(1)$ therefore, $\{2Y(n) \cdot Y(1), Y(n)^2 - Y(1), Y(n)^2 + Y(1)\}$ can generate Pythagorean triples using the terms of the Yellowstone Permutation sequence.

Example 4.6. Find the Pythagorean triple generated by terms $Y(9) = 5$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Solution:

$$2Y(n) = 2Y(9) = 2 \cdot 5 = \mathbf{10}$$

Then since $Y(1) = 1$

$$Y(n)^2 - Y(1) = Y(9)^2 - 1 = 5^2 - 1 = 25 - 1 = \mathbf{24}$$

Lastly,

$$Y(n)^2 + Y(1) = Y(9)^2 + 1 = 5^2 + 1 = 25 + 1 = \mathbf{26}$$

Therefore, the generated Pythagorean triple is (10, 24, 26).

Example 4.7. Find the Pythagorean triple generated by terms

$Y(25) = 26$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Solution:

$$2Y(n) = 2Y(25) = 2 \cdot 26 = \mathbf{52}$$

Then since $Y(1) = 1$

$$Y(n)^2 - Y(1) = Y(25)^2 - 1 = 26^2 - 1 = 676 - 1 = \mathbf{675}$$

Lastly,

$$Y(n)^2 + Y(1) = Y(25)^2 + 1 = 26^2 + 1 = 676 + 1 = \mathbf{677}$$

Therefore, the generated Pythagorean triple of the Yellowstone permutation number $Y(25) = 26$ is (52, 675, 677).

The Pythagorean triple in the last example, which is, (52, 675, 677) is called a primitive Pythagorean triple. Note that the triple is primitive when the gcd of the triple is 1.

In the next discussion, the study establishes that some terms in the Yellowstone permutation sequence generate primitive Pythagorean triple.

Generating Primitive Pythagorean triple

Consider the terms of the Yellowstone permutation sequence $Y(n)$ and $Y(n + 1)$. This is to establish that the expressions $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$, $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$, and $Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ form a Pythagorean triple. And most importantly, the triple generates a primitive Pythagorean triple. To do this, it is needed to establish the following propositions:

Proposition 4.11. Let $Y(n)$ and $Y(n + 1)$ be Yellowstone permutation numbers. If $\{(2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2)\}$ generates a primitive Pythagorean triple, then the numbers $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ cannot be both even.

Proof: Let us claim that $\{(2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2)\}$ generates a primitive Pythagorean triple. Then suppose that $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ are both even, that gives $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n) = 2p$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2| = 2q$ for some integers p and q. Combining the terms, we will have $[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 + |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|^2 = (2p)^2 + (2q)^2$.

Simplifying both sides of the last expression, $4Y(n + 1)^2 \cdot Y(n)^2 + Y(n + 1)^4 - 2Y(n + 1)^2 \cdot Y(n)^2 + Y(n)^4 = 4p^2 + 4q^2$

$$Y(n + 1)^4 + 4Y(n + 1)^2 \cdot Y(n)^2 - 2Y(n + 1)^2 \cdot Y(n)^2 + Y(n)^4 = 4(p^2 + q^2)$$

$$Y(n + 1)^4 + 2Y(n + 1)^2 \cdot Y(n)^2 + Y(n)^4 = 4(p^2 + q^2) [Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2][Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2] = 4(p^2 + q^2)$$

$$[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2 = 4(p^2 + q^2)$$

This tells us that $4 \mid [Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$ and more over $2 \mid Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$, this makes us conclude that $Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ is also even. Thus the $\gcd\{2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2\} = 2$ which contradicts our assumption that they are primitive Pythagorean triple. Therefore, $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ cannot be both even.

Proposition 4.12. Let $Y(n)$ and $Y(n + 1)$ be Yellowstone permutation numbers. If $\{(2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2)\}$ is a primitive Pythagorean triple then $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ cannot be both odd.

Proof: Claim that $\{(2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2)\}$ generates a primitive Pythagorean triple. Suppose that $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ are both odd, then we can express them as $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n) = 2p + 1$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2| = 2q + 1$ for some integers p and q. Combining the terms in the form of Pythagorean theorem, we will have $[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 + [|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|]^2 = (2p + 1)^2 + (2q + 1)^2$

Since

$$[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 + [|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|]^2 = [Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$$

then

$$[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2 = (4p^2 + 4p + 1) + (4q^2 + 4q + 1) [Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2 = 4(p^2 + q^2 + p + q) + 2$$

The last expression tells us that $[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$ is even. Also, $Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ must be even. This also further concludes that both $Y(n + 1)$ and $Y(n)$ are of the same parity. They cannot be both even since it will contradict the definition of Yellowstone permutation sequence. If they are both odd, then $[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$ must be divisible 4 to make its root a perfect square, which is a contradiction. This makes $[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$ not a square of a natural number thus, makes it not a Primitive

Pythagorean triple. Therefore, $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ cannot be both odd.

Proposition 4.13. In a primitive Pythagorean triple $\{(2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2)\}$, the terms $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ should be in opposite parity.

Proof: Given that $[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 + [|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|]^2 = [Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$ and assume that $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ is even. Therefore, the expression $[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 + [|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|]^2$ is even. If that's the case, the expression $[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2]^2$ must be even. Likewise, $Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ is even. Therefore, all the terms or expressions $(2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2)$ are all even. This is a contradiction since they are primitive Pythagorean triple.

Hence, in a Primitive Pythagorean triple $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ should be in opposite parity.

From the last proposition, $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ are in opposite parity, it gives us a value of $Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ that is odd. Furthermore, since $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ is even. Let $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n) = 2k$, which gives us $[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 = 4k^2$. Also, since $[2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 = 4pq$ then $4k^2 = 4pq$, moreover $k^2 = pq$. we also have $[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|] = 2p$ and $[Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|] = 2q$ thus $p = \frac{Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|}{2}$ and $q = \frac{Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|}{2}$

From the previous discussions, the study has already established the following information.

In a Primitive Pythagorean Triple) $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n)$ and $|Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ should be in opposite parity and $Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ is odd $k^2 = pq$

$$p = \frac{Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|}{2}$$

$$q = \frac{Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|}{2}$$

The next discussion, the study establishes that p and q are coprime.

Proposition 4.14. Let $Y(n)$ and $Y(n + 1)$ be Yellowstone permutation numbers. If $p = \frac{Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|}{2}$ $q = \frac{Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|}{2}$ then p and q are coprime.

Proof: Suppose that that p and q are not coprime. Then the gcd of p and q be some integer d not equal to 1. By definition of gcd, d

divides p and q ($d|p$ and $d|q$) then $d|(p+q)$. Notice that, $p+q = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2| + Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$

$$p+q = 2[Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2]$$

$$p+q = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2$$

Hence $d|Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2$. Similarly, if $d|2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n)$ then

$d|\gcd(|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2)$, and since the $\gcd(|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2) = 1$ this gives us $d|1$. This forces to say that $d = 1$. Therefore, p and q are coprime.

In this part, the study will now show that the previous claim, that the expressions $(2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n), |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2)$ generate a primitive Pythagorean triple.

Proposition 4.15. A Primitive Pythagorean triple can be generated by $\{|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n), Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2\}$ respectively, where $Y(n+1)$ and $Y(n)$ are coprime.

Proof: Notice that $pq = k^2$ which makes is a perfect square where p and q are coprime. It follows that p and q are also perfect squares. We let $p = Y(n+1)^2$ and $q = Y(n)^2$ with $\gcd(Y(n+1), Y(n)) = 1$. Since $p = Y(n+1)^2$ and $q = Y(n)^2$, and then, $p = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ and $q = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ and $Y(n+1)^2 = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$

$$\text{Moreover, } Y(n)^2 = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$$

$$2Y(n+1)^2 = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2| \text{ and } 2Y(n)^2 = Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|.$$

Observe that $[|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|]^2 = [Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 - |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|][Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 + |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|]$ then by substitution $[2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n)]^2 = 2Y(n+1)^2 \cdot 2Y(n)^2$, moreover, it gives us exactly $2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n)$ and follows $|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$ and $Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2$. Therefore, a primitive Pythagorean triple can be generated by $\{|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2|, 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n), Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2\}$ respectively, where $Y(n+1)$ and $Y(n)$ are coprime. ■

Example 4.8. Find the Pythagorean triple generated by terms $Y(31) = 18$ and $Y(32) = 85$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

$$\text{Solution: } 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n) = 2Y(32) \cdot Y(31) = 2(85) \cdot 18 = \mathbf{3060}$$

$$\text{Then } |Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2| = |Y(32)^2 - Y(31)^2| = (85^2 - 18^2) = 7225 - 324 = \mathbf{6901}$$

Lastly, $Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 = Y(32)^2 + Y(31)^2 = 85^2 + 18^2 = 7225 + 324 = \mathbf{7549}$ Therefore, the generated Pythagorean triple is (3060, 6901, 7549). The next question is, are the generated values (3060, 6901, 7549) primitive Pythagorean triple? To answer this, solve the gcd of (3060, 6901, 7549), that is

The prime factors of 3060 are $\{2,2,3,3,3,5,5\}$

The prime factors of 6901 are $\{67,103\}$

And lastly, 7549 is already a prime number.

Hence, the $\gcd(3060, 6901, 7549) = 1$. Therefore, the values are primitive Pythagorean Triple.

Example 4.9. Find the Primitive Pythagorean triple generated by terms $Y(12) = 12$ and $Y(13) = 35$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

$$\text{Solution: } 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n) = 2Y(13) \cdot Y(12) = 2(35) \cdot 12 = \mathbf{840}$$

Then

$$|Y(n+1)^2 - Y(n)^2| = |Y(13)^2 - Y(12)^2| = (35^2 - 12^2) = 1225 - 144 = \mathbf{1081}$$

Lastly,

$$Y(n+1)^2 + Y(n)^2 = Y(13)^2 + Y(12)^2 = (35^2 + 12^2) = 1225 + 144 = \mathbf{1369}$$

The generated Pythagorean triple is (840, 1081, 1369).

Are the generated values (840, 1081, 1369) primitive

Pythagorean triples? Finding the gcd of (840, 1081, 1369)

The prime factors of 840 are $\{2,2,2,3,5,7\}$

The prime factors of 1081 are $\{23,47\}$

The prime factors of 1369 are {37,37}

Observe that they have common prime factors, hence, the $gcd(840, 1081, 1369) = 1$. Therefore, the values are primitive Pythagorean triple.

Generating Pythagorean Quadruple

Yellowstone permutation numbers can also be used to generate Pythagorean quadruple as shown in the following theorems.

Theorem 4.16. Let $Y(n)$, $Y(n + 1)$, $Y(n + 2)$, and $Y(n + 3)$ be four consecutive terms of Yellowstone permutation sequence. Then the quantities $2Y(n) \cdot Y(n + 2) + 2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n + 3)$, $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n + 2) - 2Y(n) \cdot Y(n + 3)$, $|Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$, $Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2$ are Pythagorean quadruple.

Proof: To show that the quantities are Pythagorean quadruple, first, find the sum of the squares of $\{2Y(n) \cdot Y(n + 2) + 2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n + 3)$, $2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n + 2) - 2Y(n) \cdot Y(n + 3)$, and $|Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2|$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2(2Y(n)Y(n + 2) + 2Y(n + 1)Y(n + 3)) \\
 & + (2Y(n + 1)Y(n + 2) - 2Y(n)Y(n + 3)) \\
 & + (Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2) \\
 & = (4Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 + 8Y(n)Y(n + 1)Y(n + 2)Y(n + 3) \\
 & + 4Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2) + (4Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2 \\
 & - 8Y(n)Y(n + 1)Y(n + 2)Y(n + 3) + 4Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2) \\
 & + ((Y(n + 2)^4 + Y(n + 2)2Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 2)^2 Y(n)^2 \\
 & - Y(n + 2)2Y(n)^2) + ((Y(n + 2)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 3)^4 \\
 & - Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2) - ((Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2 \\
 & + Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 1)^4 - Y(n + 1)2Y(n)^2) \\
 & - (Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n)2Y(n + 1)^2 \\
 & - Y(n)^4))
 \end{aligned}$$

Then expanding the expressions on the right-hand side of the last equation,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{LHS} & = 4Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 + 4Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2 + 4Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2 \\
 & + 4Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 2)^4 + Y(n + 2)2Y(n + 3)^2 \\
 & - Y(n + 2)2Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n + 2)2Y(n)^2 \\
 & + Y(n + 2)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 3)^4 - Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2 \\
 & - Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2 \\
 & - Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 1)^4 + Y(n + 1)2Y(n)^2 \\
 & - Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 - Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n)2Y(n + 1)^2 \\
 & + Y(n)^4 \\
 & = Y(n)^4 + 2Y(n)2Y(n + 1)^2 + 2Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 + 2Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 \\
 & + Y(n + 1)^4 + 2Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2 \\
 & + 2Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 2)^4 \\
 & + 2Y(n + 2)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 3)^4 \\
 \text{LHS} & = Y(n)^4 + Y(n)2Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)2Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 \\
 & + Y(n)2Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n)2Y(n + 3)^2 \\
 & + Y(n + 1)^4 + Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 1)2Y(n + 2)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ Y(n+1)2Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+2)4 \\
 &+ Y(n+2)2Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+2)2Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+3)4 \\
 &= (Y(n)4 + Y(n)2Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2Y(n+2)2 + Y(n)2Y(n+3)2) \\
 &+ (Y(n+1)4 + Y(n)2Y(n+1)2 + Y(n+1)2Y(n+2)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+1)2Y(n+3)2) \\
 &+ (Y(n+2)4 + Y(n+1)2Y(n+2)2 + Y(n)2Y(n+2)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+2)2Y(n+3)2) \\
 &+ (Y(n+3)4 + Y(n)2Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2Y(n+3)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+2)2Y(n+3)2) \\
 &= Y(n)2(Y(n)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2) + Y(n+1)2(Y(n)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+1)2 + Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2) \\
 &+ Y(n+2)2(Y(n)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n+2)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+3)2) + Y(n+3)2(Y(n)2 + Y(n+1)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying the last expression,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{LHS} &= (Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2)(Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2 \\
 &+ Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2) \\
 &= (Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2)2
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the sum of the squares of $\{2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+2) + 2Y(n+1) \cdot$

$Y(n+3), 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n+2) - 2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+3),$ and $|Y(n+2)2+Y(n+3)2 -$

$Y(n+1)2 - Y(n)2|$ is the square of $Y(n+2)2 + Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2$ therefore, $\{2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+2) + 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n+3), 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n+2) - 2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+3), |Y(n+2)2+Y(n+3)2 - Y(n+1)2 - Y(n)2|, Y(n+2)2+Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2\}$ are Pythagorean quadruple.

Example 4.10. Find the Pythagorean quadruple generated by $Y_4 = 4, Y_5 = 9, Y_6 = 8,$ and $Y_7 = 15$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Solution: Firstly,

$$2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+2) + 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n+3) = 2(4)(8) + 2(9)(15) = 64 + 270 = \mathbf{334}$$

Secondly,

$$2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n+2) - 2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+3) = 2(9)(8) - 2(4)(15) = |144 - 120| = \mathbf{24}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |Y(n+2)2+Y(n+3)2 - Y(n+1)2 - Y(n)2| &= |(8)2+(15)2 - [(9)2 + (4)2] \\
 &= |64 + 225 - (81 + 16)| = |289 - (97)| = \mathbf{192}
 \end{aligned}$$

Lastly,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y(n+2)2+Y(n+3)2 + Y(n+1)2 + Y(n)2 &= (8)2+(15)2 + [(9)2 + (4)2] \\
 &= 64 + 225 + (81 + 16) = 289 + (97) = \mathbf{386}
 \end{aligned}$$

The generated Pythagorean quadruple is (334, 24, 192, 386). Example 4.11. Find the Pythagorean quadruple generated by $Y_{15} = 7, Y_{16} = 10, Y_{17} = 21,$ and $Y_{18} = 20$ of the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Solution: Firstly,

$$2Y(n) \cdot Y(n+2) + 2Y(n+1) \cdot Y(n+3) = 2(7)(21) + 2(10)(20) = 294 + 40 = \mathbf{694}$$

Secondly,

$$2Y(n + 1) \cdot Y(n + 2) - 2Y(n) \cdot Y(n + 3) = 2(10)(21) - 2(7)(20) = 420 - 28 = \mathbf{140}$$

Then,

$$|Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 3)^2 - Y(n + 1)^2 - Y(n)^2| = |(21)^2 + (20)^2 - [(10)^2 + (7)^2]|$$

$$= |441 + 400 - (100 + 49)| = |841 - (149)| = \mathbf{692}$$

Lastly,

$$Y(n + 2)^2 + Y(n + 3)^2 + Y(n + 1)^2 + Y(n)^2 = |(21)^2 + (20)^2 + [(10)^2 + (7)^2]|$$

$$= |441 + 400 + (100 + 49)| = |841 + (149)| = \mathbf{990}$$

The generated Pythagorean Quadruple is (694, 140, 692, 990).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

The Yellowstone permutation sequence has given a unique permutation and arrangement of positive integers. The rules used to generate the terms of the sequence ensure that all positive integers are present but somehow unpredictable in terms of their position.

The Yellowstone permutation sequence has unique properties. Several propositions were formulated as additional properties of the sequence.

The terms of the Yellowstone Permutation sequence established a strong relationship in generating Pythagorean triples (both primitive and non-primitive) and Pythagorean quadruples.

These recommendations aim to broaden the scope of research on the Yellowstone permutation sequence, leveraging its unique properties for practical applications and interdisciplinary exploration.

Given its unique arrangement and behavior, exploring its applications in other areas of mathematics, such as number theory and algebraic structures, could yield significant insights. Investigating the sequence's behavior under different mathematical operations and transformations may uncover new properties and relationships, such as follows:

Further study of the Yellowstone Permutation sequence by establishing its generators. Also, this can be enhanced and extended to other integer sequences.

Formulate different equations that will generate Pythagorean triple and Quadruple from the terms of the Yellowstone Permutation sequence.

Investigate and expose other integer sequences related to the Yellowstone permutation sequence.

Propose formulas that can generate a primitive Pythagorean quadruple.

Expose the relationships of the Yellowstone permutation sequence to other mathematical concepts.

Considering the unpredictable yet structured nature of the Yellowstone permutation sequence, researchers should explore its potential applications in cryptography and computer science. Its properties could be leveraged to develop new cryptographic algorithms or enhance existing ones. Furthermore, the sequence's ability to generate Pythagorean triples and quadruples might have implications for algorithm design and data encryption techniques.

While the current study is primarily theoretical, future studies should incorporate empirical and computational methods to analyze the Yellowstone permutation sequence. Developing software tools or algorithms to generate and visualize the sequence on a large scale could provide practical insights and facilitate a deeper understanding of its properties. Such computational approaches can also help in identifying patterns and anomalies that may not be evident through theoretical analysis alone.

The unique characteristics of the Yellowstone permutation sequence suggest potential applications beyond pure mathematics. Collaborative research involving mathematicians, computer scientists, and engineers could explore its use in various scientific and engineering domains. For instance, its properties might be relevant in signal processing, network theory, or even biological systems modeling, where complex and unpredictable patterns are common.

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